

INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AS A FACTOR OF ENSURING ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.

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Annotation:

This article talks about competition and competitiveness, factors affecting the competitiveness of higher education institutions, issues of education system and economic integration. A series of analyses of higher education institutions' performance indicators are also presented, including data on their coverage and number of graduates. The relationship between the higher education system and economic development is explained.

Keywords: competition, competitiveness, integration, competitiveness of higher education institutions.

The higher education system plays an important role in ensuring the country's development and industrial development. For this purpose, today every country pays attention to human capital, its further development, and the quality of education. If we take the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan alone, in the last seven years, the level of coverage in preschool education has increased from 27% to 72%, and in higher education from 9% to 42%. Although the non-state educational services of developed countries, including Germany, Great Britain, and Asian countries, China, Singapore, South Korea, and Japan, are organized in different ways, the organization of educational and methodological work in them is also positive. is distinguished by its sides.

As a result of these international observations, it is time to bring the higher education system of our country to a new level. Because we need to raise a generation that has acquired modern knowledge and technologies. The first task will be to continuously increase the level of coverage of the population with higher education.

In the following years, the entry of the non-state and private sector, many foreign higher education institutions and branches into the higher education system was a positive situation. On the one hand, the scope of higher education expands, and on the other hand, it ensures positive competition between state and non-state educational institutions, and the laws of the market begin to work in the system.

Scheme 1

The above information is also a vivid example of the attention paid to the social sphere, in particular, higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In 2023 alone, compared to 2012, the number of higher education institutions increased from 64 to 219, i.e. by 242.2%.

Scheme 2

If we analyze the number of private higher education institutions, in 2018, their number was 1, and by the end of 2023, the number of non-state higher education institutions will be 90.

Competition is a key factor for a favorable economic environment by encouraging firms to be more efficient and to offer better conditions to consumers. By competing with each other, companies become more competitive, innovative, and efficient, based on merit. This market dynamic makes the economy grow, creating jobs and well-being for society.

The competitive dynamics promote competitiveness and the efficiency of companies ensuring better prices. When companies create [cartels](#) or get involved in other [anticompetitive practices](#), the exact opposite happens — costs rise and consumers are harmed. In a market governed by openness and equity, everyone has the same opportunities. Competition promotes freedom of initiative, the right of anyone to create a business and enter the market. Therefore, the Competition Law prohibits and the Competition Authority sanctions the [abuse of a dominant position](#).

Clearly the educational provisions within any given country represent one of the main determinants of the composition and growth of that country's output and exports and constitute an important ingredient in a system's capacity to borrow foreign technology effectively. For example: health and nutrition, and primary and secondary education all raise the productivity of workers, rural and urban; secondary education, including vocational, facilitates the acquisition of skills and managerial capacity; tertiary education supports the development of basic science, the appropriate selection of technology imports and the domestic adaptation and development of technologies; secondary and tertiary education also represent critical elements in the development of key institutions, of government, the law, and the financial system, among others, all essential for economic growth. Education is indispensable to economic development. No economic development is possible without good education. A balanced education system promotes not only economic development, but productivity, and generates individual income per capita. Its influence is noticeable at the micro level of an individual family.

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